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Understanding coffee tourism development through the dynamic capabilities lens: a qualitative cross-national exploration

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ABSTRACT

This research contributes to a deeper empirical and conceptual understanding of coffee tourism development. By using a qualitative cross-national approach encompassing five coffee producing nations and guided by the dynamic capabilities framework, this study examines the potential, capitalisation and further consolidation of coffee tourism. The experiences of coffee firm leaders were gathered through semi-structured open-ended interviews; the qualitative analysis uncovered 12 overarching dimensions and helped craft a conceptual framework, with implications for understanding coffee tourism development from a practitioner and conceptual perspective. For instance, coffee tourism's potential is mainly explained by the visitor-centred and firm-centred dimensions, while the individual firm and upstream supply-chain capitalisation dimensions illuminate capitalisation demonstrations. The findings also exhibited relationships with the dynamic capabilities framework. Among these, educational experiences elucidate coffee tourism's potential (sensing) the capitalization of financial gains (seizing) while working alongside the government underlines further tourism development (reconfiguring). Various differences were also noted between countries and regions.

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Introduction

Recent developments demonstrate the significant changes taking place within the tourism industry (Sharma et al., 2021), as well as shifts in travellers' needs and demands (Pencarelli, 2020). This dynamic environment creates opportunities and presents challenges for destinations' stakeholders, including businesses providing products and services. In the context of city tourism, visitors are increasingly venturing into off-the-beaten-path destinations over those more traditional tourism business districts and old city centres in search of historical and cultural diversity that reflects a place's true identity (Matoga & Pawłowska, 2018). This phenomenon corroborates earlier assertions that many individuals want to break away from established travelling norms and conventions or from restricting homogeneity to embrace neolocalism, which underscores the deliberate search for regional lore and to reestablish links with local settings, communities and economies (Schnell & Reese, 2003; Shortridge,

1996). Neolocalism also implies the potential for the diversification of available tourism offers to address the needs of visitors searching for unique experiences (Carrillo & Barbieri, 2025).

These notions exhibit linkages to special interest tourism, which encompasses tourism types that lay emphasis on activities that draw small numbers of highly devoted visitors; one of these activities is coffee tourism (Smith et al., 2019). Coffee is mainly produced in the Southern Hemisphere, yet is mainly consumed in the Northern Hemisphere (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations, FAO, 2025). This contrast suggests the potential for coffee tourism to be pitched at an international level while benefiting many of the 125 million individuals whose livelihood depends on this industry (United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, UNCTAD, 2022).

Jolliffe et al. (2010) identified coffee tourism as a subgroup of culinary tourism, which can range from producer visits and food festivals to luxury dining or even street food experiences (Wondirad & Verheye, 2023).

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Culinary tourism, therefore, has arisen as a fundamental element of a destination's visitor products, enhancing visitors' experiences through their cultural identity (Wondirad & Verheye, 2023). Coffee tourism is also part of those pursuits embedded in local cultures, and both the product and environment are antecedents of the creation of captivating tourism experiences (Vu et al., 2023). For instance, Chen et al. (2021a) present the coffee culture in Ho Chi Minh (Vietnam), which has undergone a continuous and dynamic evolution, 'gradually becoming a "pilgrimage" site for coffee enthusiasts' (p. 2236).

Coffee tourism could, therefore, be an invaluable and competitive asset of a nation's destination image, conceptualised as 'a perception of a destination as reflected in the quality of its tourism offerings' (Lai et al., 2020, p. 928) such as attractions and infrastructure (accommodation, dining facilities). Jolliffe and Bui (2006) conceptualised coffee tourism as an activity that, beyond coffee drinking, entails the consumption of a destination's history, culture and traditions. Furthermore, coffee tourism represents one type of commodity tourism, affording opportunities for visitors to immerse in a multiplicity of experiential activities in locations that comprise cultural and natural elements connected to the coffee product (Yun, 2014). For coffee growers, coffee tourism provides a diversification avenue that could help alleviate the risks of rural regions' abandonment, persuading younger generations to remain on the land (Candelo et al., 2019).

With coffee being one of the world's most popular beverages and traded commodities (FAO, 2025), delving into this industry's diversification by embracing coffee tourism could produce insightful practitioner and conceptual knowledge. While coffee tourism scholarship has exponentially increased (e.g. Anbalagan & Lovelock, 2014; Chen et al., 2021a; Dinis et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2019; Woyesa & Kumar, 2021; Yeap et al., 2021), this phenomenon is still in its initial stages. The coffee tourism literature has mostly emerged in recent years, and, consequently, practice and theoretical scholarship are still underdeveloped (Chen et al., 2021b). Moreover, as with tea tourism research, few authors have engaged in interdisciplinary frameworks to examine coffee tourism (Chen et al., 2021b). Similarly, Smith et al. (2019) identified a lack of applied and theoretical research focusing on different coffee-related aspects, including tourism, hospitality and development.

Given the merit of further examining the coffee tourism phenomenon and the various lacunas and suggested calls for future research, this study has various objectives illustrating as many contributions.

First, drawing on data gathered among coffee business owners/managers, the study will explore (a) their perceived opportunities and challenges of coffee tourism involvement, (b) outcomes from such involvement, and (c) how coffee tourism could be further developed, thereby addressing some of the aforementioned research gaps. Second, the study data collection took place in five nations, thus providing a cross-national perspective; in this context, Chen et al. (2021b) suggest the value of future cross-cultural research in coffee or tea research. Third, the study will contribute to conceptual understanding, developing various dimensions and a theoretical framework based on qualitative content analysis and data structure methods.

To examine the proposed themes that suggest the identification of opportunities and threats, how these could be capitalised or addressed, and the way to move forward in coffee tourism development, the study considers and assesses the usefulness of the dynamic capabilities framework (e.g. Teece, 2007) in the context of coffee tourism development. Contemporary tourism research has drawn on this framework to understand resilience in the aftermath of crises and disruptive events (e.g. Shrestha & L'Espoir Decosta, 2023). More aligned with the present research, the framework has been embraced to illuminate tourism development and related improvements (e.g., Duarte Alonso et al., 2018, 2020; Gupta et al., 2024).

Literature review

Dynamic capabilities

In their ground-breaking contribution, Teece et al. (1997) referred to dynamic capabilities as firms' capacity to generate, incorporate and redesign their competences within their internal and external context to address the changes that are occurring at a rapid pace within their environment. This conceptualisation fits within the context of the coffee industry, with implications for the development of coffee tourism. For instance, Volsi et al. (2019) report on the significant changes in coffee production in Brazil, the largest coffee producer (USDA, 2024), with consumer markets' increased focus on coffee's quality and production processes. Coffee's de-commoditisation (Handino et al., 2019) and diversification into coffee tourism also underscore critical phenomena demonstrative of the swift changes within this industry. Contemporary research underlines coffee tourism's potential to help increase farms' income while discouraging deforestation (Woyesa & Kumar, 2021). This socioeconomic change is complemented by cultural and educational elements. As an illustration, Candelo

et al. (2019) suggest that diversification can elevate coffee's appeal among visitors and residents and increase awareness and knowledge of the local heritage, culture and farming techniques.

Teece's subsequent contributions delved deeper into the groundwork of the dynamic capabilities approach. For instance, Teece (2007) referred to the microfoundations of dynamic capabilities to underscore the strategic significance of procedures, distinct skills, decision rules, processes and organisational structures that strengthen three crucial clusters decisive for firms' competitiveness as they are challenging to acquire or deploy:

Sensing refers to environmental scanning, where an organisation's system collects unstructured data and disorganised information pertaining to the external environment to be assessed and handled (Teece, 2018), thereby helping identify opportunities and threats. In this scanning process, the organisation is engaged in learning, interpretive and creating activities (Teece, 2007). More related to this study's central theme, sensing also encompasses awareness of latent demand, responses among competitors and suppliers, and 'the structural evolution of industries and markets' (Teece, 2007, p. 1322).

While no studies have empirically assessed the conceptual value of the dynamic capabilities' clusters in coffee tourism development inquiry, a growing body of wine tourism development research has evaluated them (e.g. Duarte Alonso et al., 2023; Duarte Alonso & Kok, 2021; Lavandoski et al., 2018). Sustainable wine tourism development research conducted in various wine regions (Duarte Alonso et al., 2020) revealed sensing through five perceived potential benefits among wineries. Moreover, beyond financial and socioeconomic gains, increased exposure, growth (e.g. through wine exports), and the potential to incorporate gastronomy to make the winery experience more wholesome were emerging attributes (Duarte Alonso et al., 2020).

Candelo et al.'s (2019) exploration of coffee tourism's potential benefits for coffee growers and their local communities based on various stakeholder perspectives, a case study (Costa Rica) and a literature review could be considered in the context of sensing. Candelo et al.'s (2019) analysis illustrates that diversification, empowerment, the development of a region's destination image, and economic, social and environmental sustainability are perceived benefits for coffee growers. For tourists, benefits include a more diverse experience, the perception of incurring sustainability-related expenditures and consumption and increased awareness (Candelo et al., 2019).

A further demonstration of sensing in the context of coffee tourism is based on the work of Karlson and

Karlson (2009). Incorporating Murphy's (1985) proposed stages of tourism community development, Karlson and Karlson (2009) suggest that, initially, adventurous visitors with modest ambitions regarding tourist facilities enter a community. Using this contribution as an example, at this stage, the local business community senses the growth of tourism and new developments to cater for visitors' needs and wants may occur. Based on these premises, there is merit in exploring the following research question from the supply-side of coffee tourism:

Research question 1: To what extent do coffee-growing business leaders 'sense' coffee tourism's potential development in their nation?

Seizing: Upon sensing a new opportunity in the market or through technology, firms need to address, for instance, developing new processes, services or products, which almost inevitably demands investments (Teece, 2007). More strategically, seizing encapsulates the swiftness in which a system acts upon opportunities or threats once these have been detected and their importance has been ascertained (Teece, 2018). While investing in new technologies is a recurrent theme in the dynamic capabilities literature, the design, update, or implementation of business models for a variety of services or products is also vital (Teece, 2018). Duarte Alonso et al. (2020) found that the development of wine tourism activities, more professionalism (e.g. staff training), more collaboration among wineries, and elevating the appeal of the region's gastronomy were closely related to the mobilisation of resources to capitalise on opportunities.

In line with Murphy's (1985) second stage of tourism community development, Karlson and Karlson (2009) posit that a community's increased popularity and accessibility may result in higher visitor arrivals; nevertheless, at this point, coffee tourism only represents a supplementary activity or 'tertiary attraction'. Despite coffee tourism's seemingly modest role compared to other more lucrative coffee-growing activities, seizing could be illustrated by a boost in community infrastructure and activity development to cater for future visitors.

The above notions highlighting the role of seizing in the competitiveness process suggest the importance of exploring the following question:

Research question 2: How do coffee-producing firms' leaders perceive 'seizing' in the context of coffee tourism's potential?

Reconfiguring: As firms grow, changes in their business environment occur. Thus, reconfiguration is fundamental in order to keep organisational evolutionary fitness while escaping detrimental path dependencies (Teece, 2007). While success may be based and dependent upon

routines developed to achieve operational efficiency, these might be revisited when a shift in the environment occurs, leading to increased costs and internal resistance to change (Teece, 2007). Furthermore, reconfiguring entails periodic minor transformations to stay aligned with the business environment (Teece, 2018). Although nurturing experimentation and flexibility as part of an organisational culture can be challenging for organisations, these elements afford a strong foundation for simpler and nimbler transformations and, by extension, future advantages (Teece, 2018).

As these notions underline, reconfiguring can take various forms. An illustration from sustainable wine tourism research (Duarte Alonso et al., 2020) identifies the need to minimise damage to the natural resources, urban development that threatens vineyards' space, visitor carrying capacity and city traffic congestion to maintain the appeal of wineries and wine production. Further delving into Murphy's (1985) model, Karlson and Karlson (2009) highlight the third stage of tourism community development. In this stage, the community has become a magnet to numerous visitors who have become more demanding concerning their needs for more availability of attractions and facilities. To align with the reconfiguring cluster to examine coffee tourism's development, the following question is also proposed:

Research question 3: How could reconfiguration be operationalised to continue capitalising on coffee tourism's potential?

By addressing the above research questions, the study will also assess the value of considering the dynamic capabilities framework in the context of coffee tourism development.

Methodology

Approaches and methods

Given the recent emergence of the coffee tourism literature and the resulting underdeveloped stage of its theoretical and practical foundation (Chen et al., 2021b; Smith et al., 2019), this study chooses an exploratory approach and a qualitative method. Exploratory and qualitative research share various commonalities; for instance, both are undertaken when the 'problem' or 'issue' is relatively unknown or when information is scant or outdated (Hair et al., 2020; Morse, 1996).

Qualitative research enables researchers to explain and describe social settings and 'make sense of reality' (Morse, 1996, p. 1); its main focus is to learn the meanings associated with an issue or problem from participants' perspectives, as opposed to the meanings

brought by researchers (Creswell, 2009). Qualitative research is an iterative process where researchers get closer to the phenomenon studied, producing and analysing empirical data that result in 'improved understanding to the scholarly community' (Aspers & Corte, 2019, p. 155), especially when the phenomenon is inadequately defined (Black, 1994). In the case of the present research, 'getting closer' meant understanding the potential of coffee tourism development from the perspectives of coffee business experts. The application of qualitative research through gathering these perspectives was intended to achieve some of the study's objectives, including (a) addressing the proposed interview questions, (b) enhancing the knowledge of an un-researched phenomenon more deeply, and (c) developing conceptual understanding.

Furthermore, qualitative research represents an umbrella for inductive data analysis, which encompasses a bottom-up approach, where data are organised into categories, themes and patterns to gradually increase abstractness (Creswell, 2009), which is demonstrated through the development of a theoretical model (Morse, 1996; Thomas, 2006).

While the lack of cross-national studies focusing on coffee tourism in various coffee-producing nations, particularly qualitatively, was not the main reason for conducting this type of research, the absence of cross-national studies on coffee tourism strengthened and complemented such a rationale. As with other methods, qualitative cross-national inquiry has various advantages beyond its comparative emphasis, one of them being the possibility of analysing phenomena within their social or cultural setting, concerning local practices, and in individuals' daily lives (Gómez & Kuronen, 2011). To gather valuable data to generate new knowledge and information about coffee tourism, the viewpoints of experienced coffee-producing business leaders were sought. This choice aligns with purposive or purposeful sampling, a technique that involves recruiting individuals who, based on their characteristics matching 'information-rich cases', can inform the research appropriately (Patton, 2015). For this research, several criteria for participant selection were set, including having worked in the coffee industry for a minimum of one year, working in this industry at the time of the interview and holding a leadership position (owner and/or manager).

Between March and April 2024, the contact details of 103 coffee firms operating in five nations: Bolivia, Colombia, India, Peru and Vietnam were gathered through desk research. The last four nations are listed among the leaders in coffee-growing and exporting (USDA, 2024). Bolivia was selected given its renaissance from a decline

Table 1. Demographic information of the participants, their firms and interview details.

Demographic Information	Vietnam <i>n</i> = 35	Colombia <i>n</i> = 31	India <i>n</i> = 24	Bolivia <i>n</i> = 21	Peru <i>n</i> = 20	Total <i>n</i> = 131	Total %*
The firm's age (in years)							
Between 1–5	13	6	1	4	2	26	19.8
Between 6–10	12	2	0	5	5	24	18.3
Between 11–20	4	9	2	7	9	31	23.7
21 or more	6	14	21	5	4	50	38.2
The firm's size (in full-time employees)							
Between 1–9	12	17	4	13	14	60	45.8
Between 10–49	12	8	11	5	6	42	32.1
Between 50–249	11	6	9	3	0	29	22.1
The firm's primary activities							
Exporter (international)	20	21	16	12	17	86	65.6
Coffee growing/production	21	27	13	5	10	76	58.0
Coffee retailer (domestic)	35	3	4	11	10	63	48.1
Coffee roaster	35	1	5	5	3	49	37.4
Coffee tourism/visits	5	2	4	4	7	22	16.8
Participants' role							
Owner	17	9	22	16	7	71	54.2
Manager (not owner)	18	22	2	5	13	60	45.8
Gender							
Male	26	25	18	13	15	97	74.0
Female	9	6	6	8	5	34	26.0
Years of experience in the coffee industry							
Between 1–5	6	3	2	10	2	23	17.6
Between 6–10	8	3	3	4	5	23	17.6
Between 11–20	9	12	8	7	9	45	34.4
21 or more	12	13	11	0	4	40	30.4

* Percentages were rounded off as applicable.

in coffee growing and production (Statista, 2024), which could also provide insights into the extent to which coffee tourism's potential may be perceived. After receiving university ethics approval, email contact with these businesses' owners/managers involved a short summary of the study's aims and an invitation for the recipients to be interviewed in the following weeks. This first round of contacts elicited the agreement of 77 firm leaders; however, at the end of each interview, respondents were invited to suggest a contact within their industry who would fit the study's criteria. This additional effort, which aligns with snowball sampling (Noy, 2008), led to the agreement of 54 additional firm leaders; hence, 131 interviews were carried out (Table 1).

Data collection

The questions posed as part of this research's interview protocol entail two types. First, a battery of 'ice-breaker' questions gathered firm- and participant-related information (Table 1). A second type of open-ended questions to be asked during the semi-structured interview is aligned with the dynamic capabilities approach discussed in the literature review:

Open-ended question 1: How do you perceive the potential for developing coffee tourism, including from your business/industry perspective?

Open-ended question 2: How is coffee tourism currently being capitalised within your business/industry?

Open-ended question 3: What is necessary to further develop coffee tourism within your business/industry?

The interviewees were encouraged to elaborate on their questions, providing examples and extended comments. The interviews were audio recorded with their permission, and prior to the start, they were informed that being interviewed would be deemed as their consent to participate. As noted, the three questions strongly relate to sensing, seizing, and reconfiguring, respectively; thus, several contributions pertaining to this literature were considered in the design of these questions (e.g. Teece, 2007, 2018). Similarly, contemporary coffee tourism studies were consulted (Anbalagan & Lovelock, 2014; Candelo et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2021b; Dinis et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2019; Woyesa & Kumar, 2021; Yeap et al., 2021), as well as those embracing the dynamic capabilities approach in the context of wine tourism (e.g. Duarte Alonso et al., 2018, 2020; Duarte Alonso et al., 2023; Lavandoski et al., 2018). The semi-structured interviews were conducted in English (India), Spanish (Bolivia, Colombia and Peru) and Vietnamese (Vietnam).

To translate the questions into different languages, the study sought the support of professional translators and external researchers, following principles of iterative and collaborative translation and equivalent meaning

Table 2. Pearson's Chi-Square and Cramer's V tests.

	Chi-Square and Cramer's V	Description
Figure 1 – Sensing		
Educational/learning experiences ...	$\chi^2 (4, n = 131) = 15.556, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .345)$	V* (71.4%), C (67.7%), I (70.8%), P (55.0%), B (23.8%)
Strong consideration of a business ...	$\chi^2 (4, n = 131) = 16.577, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .356)$	V* (17.1%), C (58.1%), I (45.8%), P (60.0%), B (28.6%)
Educational/learning experiences ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 5.309, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .201)$	Asia (71.2%), South America (51.4%)
Strong consideration of a business ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 6.042, (p < 0.05; \text{Cramer's } V = .215)$	Asia (28.8%), South America (50.0%)
Amalgamating coffee tourism ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 9.663, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .272)$	Asia (8.5%), South America (30.6%)
Figure 2 – Seizing		
Increases the income of different ...	$\chi^2 (4, n = 131) = 11.757, (p < 0.05; \text{Cramer's } V = .300)$	V* (31.4%), C (61.3%), I (54.2%), P (25.0%), B (28.6%)
Increases visits (e.g. to the coffee farm) ...	$\chi^2 (4, n = 131) = 16.299, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .353)$	V* (17.1%), C (41.9%), I (41.7%), P (70.0%), B (52.4%)
Increases visits (e.g. to the coffee farm) ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 8.812, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .259)$	Asia (27.1%), South America (52.8%)
Promoting the coffee business's brand	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 10.836, (p < 0.001; \text{Cramer's } V = .288)$	Asia (39.0%), South America (13.9%)
Figure 3 – Reconfiguring		
Persuading, negotiating, working ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 23.243, (p < 0.001; \text{Cramer's } V = .421)$	Asia (13.6%), South America (54.2%)
The need to engage/immerse visitors ...	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 12.109, (p < 0.001; \text{Cramer's } V = .304)$	Asia (40.7%), South America (13.9%)
Share knowledge with visitors	$\chi^2 (1, n = 131) = 7.175, (p < 0.01; \text{Cramer's } V = .234)$	Asia (37.3%), South America (16.7%)

* V: Vietnam, C: Colombia, I: India, P: Peru, B: Bolivia.

(Douglas & Craig, 2007); these principles were also embraced during the interview data translation. The average length of the semi-structured interviews was one hour; because of the geographic distance to the coffee producers, 115 of the 131 interviews (87.8%) were conducted online, with 16 being conducted onsite in Vietnam. These interviews, together with visiting an international coffee fair in Ho Chi Minh City in 2024, provided opportunities to expand and complement the acquired knowledge and, together with the cross-national and comparative aspect of the research, partly enabled triangulation (Paul, 1996). Furthermore, members of the research team were involved in the data collection, transcribing, and helping polish the translated version. While data saturation patterns emerged as early as the initial 18 interviews, the principle of data appropriateness was applied as opposed to using numerical markers to ascertain data quality and saturation (O'Reilly & Parker, 2013).

Data analysis

After transcribing the interview data, they were analysed using two methods that complement the study's inductive approach, namely, qualitative content analysis and data structure. The first method encompasses a subjective interpretation of the data, with the researcher systematically classifying the data based on coding, where themes and patterns are revealed (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). The second method, the data structure, consists of three stages, with the first focusing on creating analytical categories and codes, later compiled into a data structure entailing first-order codes that are 'informant-centric', second-order themes (researcher/theory-centric) and aggregate dimensions (Magnani & Gioia, 2023). In line with the inductive approach, the second step comprises the development of a dynamic inductive model (Gioia

et al., 2013), while in the third, researchers frequently refer to first-order informant quotations, second-order and aggregate dimensions (Magnani & Gioia, 2023). Figures 1–3 provide visualisations of the data structure. Apart from these methods and to assess potential differences between individual countries or regions (Asia: India and Vietnam versus South America: Bolivia, Colombia and Peru) based on response frequencies, Pearson's Chi-Square and Cramer's V will be used (Table 2).

Trustworthiness/rigour in qualitative research

Among other authors, Guba (1981) presented four aspects of trustworthiness in 'natural inquiry'; Shenton (2004) and Stahl and King (2020) illuminate specific paths to address them. First, following Shenton's (2004) recommendations, this methodology section captured different forms of triangulation, including choosing different sites, informants, and methods, thus, addressing issues of credibility. Second, while *transferability* is 'tricky' given that the aims of qualitative research do not include replicability (Stahl & King, 2020), in line with Shenton (2004), this study presented background data and a comprehensive description of the studied phenomenon so that future comparisons can be made. Similarly, to address *dependability*, a thorough description of the study's methodology can allow researchers to replicate the study (Shenton, 2004); this methodology section, again, illustrates such depth. Finally, by operationalising triangulation, the study aligns with Shenton's (2004) suggestion to also utilise this medium to address issues of *confirmability*.

Demographic aspects

The initial analysis (Table 1) indicates that most participating firms (105, 80.2%) have operated for six or more

Perceptions regarding sensing opportunities and threats	n=131	%
Educational/learning experiences (e.g., educating visitors, learning from visitors)	79	60.3
Integrating coffee tourism as the firm’s business model	53	40.5
The potential for immersive experiences (e.g., hands-on activities for visitors)	46	35.1
Coffee tourism strengthens the region’s destination image	36	27.5
Promoting the coffee business’s brand	30	22.9
Barriers/threats (limited government support, lack of infrastructure, danger of pollution)	29	22.1
Opportunities for offering coffee tourism tours, to develop coffee tourism routes	28	21.4
Amalgamating coffee tourism with other leisure activities (for visitors)	27	20.6
Developing coffee tourism alongside sustainable practices (in the business, in the region)	24	18.3
Showcasing the coffee business’s products	23	17.6
Fostering live-in learning, internship experiences	19	14.5
Financial benefits (selling the coffee product, charging for visits)	19	14.5
Offering onsite accommodation, retreats	18	13.7
Hosting industry representatives (e.g., importers)	13	9.9
Increasing awareness of the local culture	12	9.2
Coffee tourism is conducive to networking (e.g., with travel agents, with other businesses)	11	8.4
Coffee tourism can be operationalised throughout the year’s seasons	9	6.9
Investments made in infrastructure to offer coffee tourism	9	6.9

Figure 1. Sensing in the context of coffee tourism – Data structure. Source: Authors’ creation.

Perceptions regarding seizing opportunities from coffee tourism	n=131	%
Increases the income of different coffee supply chain players	54	41.2
Increases visits (e.g., to the coffee farm, region, country by industry people, tourists)	53	40.5
Helps improve coffee consumers' knowledge through visitation	48	36.6
Helps promote the coffee business, its products	39	29.8
Increases coffee sales	33	25.2
Strengthens the business's brand image	33	25.2
Fosters more robust networking/collaboration with other supply chain members	17	13.0
Threats (e.g., limited government support, infrastructure, accessibility)	15	11.5
Induces more rigorous production quality controls/assurance	14	10.7
Helps showcase the diversity of tastes to enhance visitors' experience	10	7.6
Triggers more interest in organising coffee-related events	9	6.9
Contributes to coffee price increases (e.g., onsite sales)	8	6.1
Has a ripple effect, motivating other producers to adopt the coffee tourism business model	5	3.8

Figure 2. Seizing in the context of coffee tourism – Data structure. Source: Authors' creation.

years; similarly, the large majority employed less than 50 full-time employees. Regarding their business activities, almost two-thirds were exporting, and nearly 60 per cent were engaged in coffee growing and other forms of production; a similar percentage of firm owners and managers took part in the study, while nearly three-fourths were male. Additionally, 108 interviewees (82.4%) have worked in the coffee industry for six or more years, thus demonstrating their value as information-rich cases in this exploration. Finally, 22 firms

(16.8%) were open to visitors, for instance, offering tours/tastings and onsite accommodation.

Results

The potential to develop coffee tourism

The first area of the analysis concerned participants' perceptions of the potential for coffee tourism development. [Figure 1](#) first illustrates three first-order

Perceptions regarding reconfiguring coffee tourism	n=131	%
Persuading, negotiating, working alongside government (e.g., to boost infrastructure)	48	36.6
Developing a long-term coffee tourism growth plan (e.g., a well-thought through process)	37	28.2
The need to engage/immerse visitors (e.g., in various coffee production activities)	34	26.0
Sharing knowledge with visitors (to elicit interest, repeat visits, brand patronage)	34	26.0
More expertise to develop coffee tourism (e.g., recruiting professionals, training)	30	22.9
Coffee tourism should be amalgamated with other experiences (not a standalone activity)	28	21.4
Thinking of coffee tourism as a niche as opposed to a mainstream/mass visitation activity	27	20.6
Selecting, studying, learning about potential visitor markets	23	17.6
Being consistent in the quality of the experience on offer (product/service)	21	16.0
Storytelling (sharing the historic/cultural value of coffee, its consumption/practices)	18	13.7
Avoiding 'casual' approaches to coffee tourism (e.g., develop official tours)	18	13.7
Maintaining a responsible production mindset (integrity in product/service delivery)	16	12.2
Improving coffee growing practices (e.g., sustainable farming, higher production quality)	14	10.7
Establishing coffee trails among coffee businesses operating within the same region	13	9.9

Figure 3. Reconfiguring in the context of coffee tourism – Data structure. Source: Authors' creation.

codes based on frequencies above 40. By far, educational/learning experiences were considered the most explicit demonstration of 'sensing' coffee tourism's potential. This finding relates to two aspects, namely, (a) coffee businesses can enhance visitors' knowledge of coffee production and related processes

and (b) businesses can also learn from visitors (e.g. through feedback). Participants' most perceived business opportunities were associated with the integration of coffee tourism as part of their business model and harnessing coffee tourism to provide visitors with immersive experiential opportunities,

including offering hands-on activities onsite. Further analysis led to the crafting of four second-order themes, with two being the most influential. The first theme encapsulates the importance of opportunities for visitors and tourists beyond hands-on, immersive experiences on the coffee farm to emphasise other aspects. Coffee tourism tours, combining coffee tourism with other leisure activities or regional attractions or with sustainable coffee-producing practices, and live-in/internship experiences were key illustrations. Also noteworthy was creating awareness of local cultures and experiencing the uniqueness of both seasonal and production features, such as flowering and harvesting, or the peeling, washing and fermenting steps thereafter. Various selected verbatim comments extend these findings:

Vietnam7: Vietnam has become a destination for travellers around the world. In the past ten years, foreigners did not know that we had coffee. Nowadays, they know that Vietnam ... produces a lot of Robusta coffee. Especially, Buon Ma Thuot has branded itself as a coffee city ... Tourists can come here during the harvesting season to experience how to harvest, dry, and roast coffee.

Colombia26 (opens to visitors): I am convinced that [coffee tourism] is the way to hook people who consume coffee ... If you manage to talk to people, you also receive information and learn a lot from them. Not only does one live from the dollar value but also from their recognition, how delicious your coffee is, how sound your farm's practices are ...

The second predominant theme represented opportunities for the firm. Apart from the adoption of coffee tourism as part of the firm's business model, opportunities were perceived through brand promotion, product showcasing, or financial benefits through visits and coffee sales. Similarly, providing accommodation or investing in infrastructure to host visitors was associated with financial returns. Further opportunities included hosting industry representatives and networking opportunities, which can further add to sales and grow the coffee firm's tourism side. A third second-order theme highlighted coffee tourism's potential to contribute to enhancing the region's or country's destination image, while other comments underlined threats in coffee tourism's developmental process. As some comments illustrate:

India20: We are receiving a lot of inquiries from our buyers as well as the main roasters who supply coffee ... We have lots of these visitors ... they can come and have a look at how we are growing coffee in a more responsible way, with a lot of flora and fauna around ... they are trying to understand how ecologically we are growing ...

Bolivia13: We exploit almost nothing in terms of tourism ... in this town, which is our coffee capital, the infrastructure is terrible ... the businesses have sought support from the government to no avail.

Calculating the response frequencies of the most prominent first-order codes based on the premise that no cell should have a count of less than five (e.g. Chan, 2003) enabled further analysis using Pearson's Chi-Square and Cramer's V (Table 2). Various statistically significant differences were noticed. Comparing individual countries revealed that higher percentages of Vietnamese, Colombian and Indian respondents indicated the relevance of educational/learning experiences as an opportunity stemming from CT's development. Higher percentages of Peruvian and Colombian participants considered integrating coffee tourism into the firm's business model. Similar outcomes were perceived when comparing Asian and South American nations. Furthermore, a higher percentage of the South American cohort perceived amalgamating coffee tourism with other leisure activities than their Asian counterparts.

Capitalising on coffee tourism's development

Queried about how coffee tourism is being capitalised at a firm or industry level, participants' observations revealed the relevance of three first-order codes, with two of these being considered almost equally (Figure 2). The first code included financial benefits for various supply chain actors and is part of a second-order theme that identifies various gains for these groups in various other forms. In this context, and partly aligned with wine tourism research (Duarte Alonso et al., 2020), coffee tourism's development can persuade industry actors to embrace networking and collaboration, organise events to share knowledge and promote the coffee industry, and motivate other coffee producers to follow these steps and embrace coffee tourism as a valuable business alternative. The first second-order theme, however, asserts coffee tourism as a source of tangible and intangible benefits that can occur as a chain reaction, such as sales or price increases, or in the form of a multiplier effect based on promotion and brand enhancement.

Peru4 (opens to visitors): I invested here on the farm. I did a lot of work with the family; we have lodging, we teach coffee production and we already have many domestic and international visits ... here we show visitors how we work and the benefits of drinking good coffee ... there is great potential, and [coffee tourism] is an extra income for us too.

Colombia1: Last January, I received a tour of 80 people from the United States looking for coffee experiences

... I had to hire 15 logistics people, I had to shop, and we sold coffee. I did not just sell my coffee but also my neighbours' coffee. We hired the drivers for the transportation for those 80 people ... It is also about the multiplier effect of that money ...

Nevertheless, challenges preventing the capitalisation of coffee tourism were also pointed out; once again, the limited involvement of government agencies in supporting coffee tourism's growth and development was ascertained. More specifically, respondents observed that the lack of infrastructure to connect cities and towns to coffee farms or limited accessibility poses serious threats to such a development:

Peru20 (opens to visitors): We would need to install cabins, showers and bathrooms close to the plots. What limits visitors? The road. It would be great if they visited us in March or April, but the access is very rough, there are landslides, so they do not risk coming.

Vietnam30 (opens to visitors): We want to create an opportunity to connect with our target customers and coffee-related organisations to build trade relationships. We also have substantial resources ... and infrastructure ... However, not every business has the conditions to develop coffee tourism ... That's why, at a broader level, the government should introduce policies and provide support for businesses that want to engage in coffee tourism.

The challenge presented by accessibility accentuates the developmental stage of coffee tourism, which might be more appropriate for unpretentious visitors (Karlson & Karlson, 2009).

Adhering to Chan's (2003) recommendation, the analysis based on frequencies allowed for making various comparisons across the participant countries and continents (Asia versus South America). Colombian and Indian participants perceived financial benefits for different supply chain actors more highly, whereas higher percentages of Peruvian and Bolivian respondents viewed the capitalisation of coffee tourism through more farm visits (Table 2). Unsurprisingly, this item was selected more highly by South American participants (52.8%), whereas the same was true among Asian participants (39.0%) regarding the capitalisation of coffee tourism by helping coffee firms promote their brand.

How coffee tourism could be developed further

The last section of the analysis (Figure 3) first illuminated a multitude of first-order codes highlighting the need for profound strategic approaches, many of which demand time and investment to establish a strong coffee tourism foundation. Indeed, developing a long-term plan,

acquiring knowledge and skills, amalgamating coffee tourism with other activities, learning about the potential visitor and consumer markets, delivering consistent, high-quality coffee products and tourism services, ensuring visitor/consumer trust by avoiding casual approaches and organising a coffee trail are all part of a strategic mindset. As Vietnam16 observed:

The knowledge about coffee in the market today is somewhat chaotic ... Traditionally, farmers and coffee producers have not been trained in sensory details. If we want to elevate coffee into a high-value product that delivers a refined experience for customers, we need service professionals who truly understand coffee craftsmanship. Right now, coffee tourism in Vietnam mainly revolves around coffee tasting, combined with sightseeing and heritage tours. However, the approach is still fragmented and underdeveloped.

Participants' responses further demonstrated the strategic value of establishing and strengthening bonds with visitors. As earlier tourism and wine tourism research has established (e.g. Frost et al., 2020), and despite its challenges, storytelling can be an influential and powerful tool to create and enhance those bonds (Vietnam1): *'Sharing experiences and stories about coffee would be a great approach, but it would also be a complex and demanding task. It would require expertise as well.'* Equally important was to engage/immerse visitors in coffee tourism, and share knowledge about coffee-growing and production aspects (Peru5):

Coffee tourism starts with an offer ... as tourist destinations and the coffee tourism circuit become consolidated, we have to put together the combos in some way. It is not just about going to the field, but also about showing visitors the washing, the roasting ...

The importance of persuasion, negotiation and working alongside the authorities was also identified as a means to receive support in various forms, particularly in infrastructure development, building permits and certifications. For instance, India14 noted the potential for 'shade-grown coffee' (coffee plants grown under a tree canopy) to be developed as a coffee tourism attraction and the role the government should play in promoting and bringing growers together in cooperatives. In turn, Bolivia8 perceived the current infrastructure as attractive to visitors who were looking for unique experiences while also stressing the government's role:

The tourists want to rediscover their roots, which they have lost ... because of the way we live, we epitomise the way of life they [the tourists] lost ... We only need support from the Ministry of Tourism, but it has to start from ourselves ... from each producer, from each cooperative ... each company must do that.

A last second-order theme complements the previous findings, underlining the crucial step of maintaining integrity in various processes and practices. Various comments referred to previous fraudulent practices that could tarnish a business's and a region's image, while others touched upon socioeconomic sustainability (Colombia13):

Human talent would play an important role, as would the skills and capabilities of the people around [coffee growing] ... We also have to think about profitability. If we want coffee tourism to be viable in the future, we have to think about the profitability of the coffee producer ...

No statistically significant differences emerged by comparing the highest frequencies associated with open-ended question 3 and the different participant groups by country, and only three were revealed concerning continents (Table 2). For instance, a higher percentage of South American participants (54.2%) indicated the importance of persuasion, negotiation and working alongside the government. Conversely, higher percentages of Asian participants perceived the need to engage/immerse visitors alongside sharing knowledge.

Discussion

At the outset, this research endeavoured to fulfil various key objectives, each associated with a contribution. First, the study explored three themes that add to the extant body of the coffee tourism literature from the supply-side (owners/managers) viewpoint, namely, perceived opportunities and threats, capitalising on coffee tourism's implementation and how coffee tourism could be developed further. Given the evolving stage of the coffee tourism literature (Chen et al., 2021b), by examining the above three foci, the study made several practical and conceptual contributions. Second, the study employed a cross-national approach, gathering data from coffee industry actors in five nations. As the analysis demonstrates, this cross-national angle revealed several differences among nations and regions, suggesting the value of considering the cross-national lens in future investigations.

Third, the study made various conceptual contributions. Among these, the crafting of 12 overarching dimensions, complemented by as many second-order themes, advances the conceptual understanding of coffee tourism related to the three key themes under inquiry. Concerning Figure 1, the 'visitor-centred' and 'firm-centred impacts' dimensions help explain and juxtapose participants' perceptions of coffee tourism's potential opportunities and threats. Here, they view numerous ways to afford wholesome experiences to

visitors while also achieving financial and non-financial goals. The 'region-centred impacts' dimension underlines a fulfilment that transcends visitors and firms to also position the region, raising its appeal through coffee tourism development. In contrast, the 'inhibited potential' dimension cautions the supply-side stakeholders regarding areas that could hinder coffee tourism's development, encouraging them to anticipate and address these barriers or threats.

Figure 2 underlines three primary ways of capitalising on coffee tourism's operationalisation. The 'individual firm capitalisation' dimension encompasses present and future positive impacts on firms' bottom line. Importantly, these impacts are primarily perceived through footfall and promotion, whereas financial outcomes (sales) represent a more distant objective. The 'upstream supply chain capitalisation' dimension signposts benefits for members of the supply chain, thus, rendering coffee tourism a more sustainable and equitable business proposition, and is reinforced by collaboration and mutual support. The 'downstream supply chain capitalisation' dimension is also related to sustainable forms of coffee tourism, encouraging firms to step up their efforts in educating visitors and consumers and also maintaining standards and integrity in their service/product offerings. As with Figure 1, the 'ominous drawbacks' dimension highlights barriers to fully capitalising on coffee tourism. This dimension also affords a mechanism to guide practitioners, namely, in decision-making, including considering future investments, in terms of strategy development or business model adaptation/development.

Figure 3 provides a well-rounded scenario of how coffee tourism is to be further developed. The 'delineating schemes' dimension guides the understanding of practitioners and researchers in devising plans and frameworks to develop coffee tourism further or consolidate current achievements, including in experiential and product-related aspects. Again, the importance of integrity is highlighted through consistency and avoidance of casual approaches, where compromising standards in the experiential delivery could jeopardise visitor trust and future consumption. The 'business-visitor rapport-building' dimension complements this point, emphasising the significance for coffee industry actors by drawing visitors' interest in coffee production, its traditions, history and cultural value. The 'exhorting for advancements' dimension illustrates the existing dilemmas that business actors face when seeking to develop a tourism idea or activity. Finally, the 'on-the-ground practices' dimension reinforces the idea that, in order to develop tourism based on agricultural products, producers must 'keep their eyes on the ball', preventing

* Denotes differences based on higher percentages across nations and continents (Asia versus South America).

Figure 4. The coffee tourism development framework. Source: Authors' creation; sources consulted: Teece (2007, 2018).

the loss of their production standards and natural environment. This issue was pinpointed by nine Colombian respondents referring to a formerly coffee-producing community that had exploited tourism to the point of massification and loss of its coffee-producing identity.

The achievement of various objectives delineated above also demonstrates the narrowing of empirical and conceptual gaps recognised in the literature (Chen et al., 2021b; Smith et al., 2019) and the insightfulness of considering the dynamic capabilities approach to examine coffee tourism development from coffee industry stakeholders' perspectives.

Theoretical implications

The study presents various theoretical implications. Overall, the crafted dimensions provide a road map to understanding different stages of coffee tourism development. In four cases, the dimensions intersect among the three themes and with the dynamic capabilities framework, thereby extending its underpinnings in this area. Firstly, the 'visitor-centred impacts' dimension, which explains one among various opportunities from coffee tourism development, intersects with the

'downstream supply chain capitalisation' dimension regarding the materialisation of opportunities and the 'business-visitor rapport-building' dimension, which highlights the perceived future of coffee tourism in terms of development, strengthening, and consolidation. The dynamic capabilities approach is valuable for deepening the understanding of these processes and emerging connections. Indeed, the sensing opportunities/threats process is highlighted as mainly revolving around visitors' experiences, needs and wants. The visitor cohort is also significant within the seizing cluster ('downstream supply chain capitalisation' dimension) and again regarding coffee tourism's reconfiguring ('business-visitor rapport building' dimension). Figure 4, therefore, underscores priorities in opportunity/threat sensing and reconfiguring, while the benefits accrued from coffee tourism for visitors are superseded by the individual coffee-producing firm and members of the coffee industry supply chain.

Secondly, and based on the response frequencies, the firm is unsurprisingly at the centre of the sensing process, as the second primary recipient of potential coffee tourism development opportunities and the first from its capitalisation (seizing), and also plays a crucial role in the reconfiguring process, for instance, through

quality assurance and integrity. These points partly align with research presenting some of the potential benefits of coffee tourism for firms and visitors (e.g. Candelo et al., 2019).

Thirdly, the framework (Figure 4) explains connections between sensing, seizing and reconfiguring and region-centred impacts. The 'delineating schemes' dimension is instrumental for both the individual firm and the region; indeed, several first-order codes align with both firms' and their region's interests (a long-term growth plan, acquiring expertise, amalgamating coffee and other leisure activities). Fourthly, the study extends the dynamic capabilities framework's principles in the context of coffee tourism development by illustrating the need to consider threats at various stages.

Whereas the dynamic capabilities underpinnings predicate the potential for threats mainly within the sensing and reconfiguring clusters (e.g. Teece 2007), this study's analysis ascertains that threats also need consideration during the seizing process of coffee tourism. Even when resources may be mobilised at a firm/industry level to capitalise on opportunities and capture value from these (Teece, 2014), the lack of regional infrastructure, the government's slowness in actioning this and other steps and the coffee farms' poor accessibility can undermine its realisation. A further theoretical implication relates to the reconfiguring cluster. A linkage is observed between the firm level. The 'on-the-ground practices' dimension underlines the significance of a responsible production mindset and improving coffee-growing practices, which can have direct impacts on the firm's sensing process ('firm-centred impacts' dimension) and, by extension, on various coffee tourism stakeholders ('upstream supply chain capitalisation' dimension).

The various relationships between the dynamic capabilities clusters and the study's themes, again, confirmed the suitability of this framework. Extending from the 12 crafted dimensions and a theoretical framework, there are implications for deepening the understanding of the emerging first-order codes (Figures 1–3), for instance, developing these into ranked items to be operationalised in future research, choosing quantitative or mixed-methods.

Practical implications

The analysis and framework (Figure 4) also underscore practical implications. First, participants' perceptions of coffee tourism's potential opportunities (Figure 1) underline implications for coffee-producing firms during this preliminary scanning process (Teece, 2007), in branching out their focus by acquiring and absorbing

knowledge to develop strategies and be ready to address opportunities and threats. The highest response frequencies (first-order codes) suggest two primary areas that are intrinsically related. Indeed, the 'visitor-centred impacts' dimension implies 'learning how to educate', or acquiring the necessary skills to host, educate, immerse and cater for visitors. While this aspect is crucial in building or reinforcing firm-visitor relationships, it can be challenging to operationalise.

Coffee-producing operators could learn from the experiences of firms offering these in the wine, food, or craft beer industries, leading as efficient communicators and educators. Doing so will inevitably affect the second area, or how coffee tourism can positively affect the coffee firm, which includes promotion, diversification, financial rewards or building industry networks. These outcomes are reinforced by the 'individual firm capitalisation' dimension (Figure 2), and, importantly, also represented by the 'upstream supply chain capitalisation', which underlines the 'domino effect' that both educating visitors and direct beneficial impacts on the firm can have more broadly at a regional level.

The analysis concerning how coffee tourism is capitalised further extends the previous implications, primarily for the firm and the various coffee industry supply chain stakeholders. In this context, the improvement of the firms' production and innovative practices (e.g. diversity of tastes) directly spills over to the visitor/consumer side, enhancing the consumption/visitation experience, thus further creating opportunities for both parties. Figure 3 also illustrates the spillover of firms' action, in this case, through the 'delineating schemes' dimension, which implies consolidating coffee tourism's development through numerous actions that underscore investments to address visitors' expectations while also achieving firm objectives. To avoid potential loss of competitiveness, and as indicated by several Colombian participants, participants could learn from these cases. Furthermore, the adoption of best practices (Teece et al., 1997) while avoiding routines that could be counterproductive in light of changes in the business environment (Teece, 2007) demands time and financial investments. Strategic development and management, enhanced professionalism, knowledge acquisition, consistency in product/service delivery and collaboration need to be prioritised (Figure 3).

Implications are also noticed from the perceived barriers and challenges in identifying potential opportunities from coffee tourism, exploiting these, and further consolidating its development. While issues related to the lack of government support, including investments in infrastructure or difficulty in persuading or engaging,

are persistent and complex, clear priority-based guidelines should exist for businesses and government representatives, for instance, compromising and working towards common goals. Finally, important implications can be drawn from the various differences across nations and regions that were revealed through the additional data analysis and that are also illustrated in [Figure 4](#). Among other premises, these differences refer to strengths and weaknesses that could inform the individual countries' coffee industry stakeholders to understand current potential and needs to elevate this activity further.

Conclusions

In applying an exploratory approach and qualitative method, together with considering a cross-national lens, and assessing the value of the dynamic capabilities approach, the study accomplished various objectives that illustrate empirical and conceptual contributions to the body of the coffee tourism literature. For instance, 12 conceptual dimensions and second-order themes emerged from the qualitative analysis. Evaluating the potential for coffee tourism development, including associated opportunities and threats, primarily illuminated the importance of experiential and educational opportunities for visitors ('visitor-centred impacts' dimension) and ways for coffee businesses to maximise coffee tourism ('firm-centred impacts' dimension). How coffee tourism was perceived to be capitalised could be explained by tangible/intangible impacts on coffee businesses ('individual firm capitalisation' dimension) and gains for coffee supply-side actors ('upstream supply chain' dimension). Finally, how coffee tourism could be further developed can be best explained by the 'delineating schemes' dimension, which is based on strategic approaches to stimulate or consolidate coffee tourism growth.

Although the study aligned with a qualitative method, additional analysis based on frequencies revealed various differences in perceptions between coffee business leaders operating in Asia (India, Vietnam) and South America (Bolivia, Colombia and Peru) as well as between countries. Regarding 'sensing,' Asian participants perceived more highly the potential for educational/learning experiences; in contrast, the amalgamation of coffee tourism with other activities was favoured more intensely among South American participants. Regarding 'seizing,' more visitation and more brand promotion appeared to be more apparent among South American and Asian businesses, respectively. With regard to 'reconfiguring,' South American participants considered persuasion, negotiation

and/or working alongside government more markedly, while Asian respondents pointed to experiential aspects of coffee tourism (engagement/immersion) more noticeably. The overarching 12 conceptual dimensions contributed to crafting a model ([Figure 4](#)) that enhances and deepens the conceptual understanding of coffee tourism development.

Limitations and future research

Despite its contributions, the study presents various limitations; some of these could be considered or addressed in future research. Empirically, the study gathered data from five nations on two continents; while two of these nations are global coffee-producing leaders, other continents and regions, including Africa or Central America, were not included. Furthermore, the country of Brazil, the world's largest coffee producer, was not included. Consequently, opportunities exist for researchers to investigate coffee tourism from the perspective of coffee industry actors elsewhere. This line of research could allow gathering useful insights. For instance, and as demonstrated in the present research, which compared five coffee-producing nations' business leaders, future research could help uncover similarities or differences in perceptions of coffee tourism development between Brazilian and other coffee-growing nations.

Conceptually, while the adoption of the dynamic capabilities framework proved insightful, its application and that of the crafted dimensions and model ([Figure 4](#)) were only considered and presented in the present research, respectively. Thus, there is a need for the robustness of these conceptual underpinnings to be further assessed in coffee tourism inquiry. Finally, the study focused on a qualitative method only, which affords opportunities for the adoption of quantitative or mixed methods in future investigations.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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Data availability statement

Data can be provided upon request.

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